

IMPROVING THE INFORMATION SUPPLY MODEL FOR THE IMPLEMENTATION OF INNOVATIVE STRATEGIES

Yuldasheva Nilufar Abduvakhidovna,
Fergana Polytechnic Institute,
Associate Professor of the Department of Management,
Doctor of Economic Sciences
e-mail: nilush1986@bk.ru
tel: +998941331615

Abstract. The article covers the issues related to information provision in the implementation of the innovative strategy to achieve the goals of innovative development of industrial enterprises. Methodological aspects of information supply in managing the strategic development process are also described.

Keywords. Innovative development, innovative strategy, strategic management, model of information provision, indicators

Introduction. Achieving the goals of strategic innovative development cannot be achieved without appropriate information, which forms the basis for making and implementing management decisions in the process of strategy development and implementation. Based on the relevant theoretical and methodological plan, the practical implementation of the methodological rules of the development strategy of the industrial enterprise, and the need to develop the tools that will allow the development strategy to be used. It meets the principles and criteria of balance and helps to achieve the goals.

Literature review. In the works of local researchers, a number of fundamental requirements for providing management decisions with information are highlighted, for example: relevance, reliability, completeness, appropriateness, information unity [3]. As for innovative activities, these requirements are not only preserved, but also become mandatory conditions that ensure the achievement of the goals of innovative development.

N.M. Tyukavkin says that informatization provides a wide range of benefits to enterprises, increases the efficiency of their activities [8]. New information systems incorporate advanced management experience, optimization of business processes in accordance with the latest achievements in management theory and practice. According to L.A.Trofimova and V.V.Trofimov, one of the main conditions for ensuring the high quality and efficiency of the management decision is to provide the decision maker with high-quality information [7].

Research methodology. Methods such as induction and deduction, analysis and synthesis, observation, structural analysis, statistical analysis, abstract-logical thinking are used in the implementation of scientific research. Literature and articles of foreign and national economists were analyzed as the methodological basis of the article.

Analysis and discussion of results.

The implementation of the concept of innovative development of industrial enterprises based on the processes of modernization and renewal of the technical and technological sphere of the enterprise and the processes of development of the existing organizational and management sphere imposes appropriate requirements on the management. The system serves to create a management system that allows not only to form an optimal portfolio of organizational and management innovation projects and their effective implementation, but also to monitor and analyze the ongoing development activities. Timely implementation of management decisions and the effectiveness of management decisions in the framework of the implementation of measures to achieve strategic goals depends on how quickly the manager receives this or that information, and how quickly he can implement the innovative strategy of the enterprise. fully represents the implementation processes.

Researchers say that currently more than twenty methods of information support are proposed for the development and implementation of innovative strategy [2]. At the same time, the analysis shows that attention is paid to the property and financial aspects of the changes related to the implementation of strategic development in the information supply systems in which the strategy has been developed, as well as the state of the enterprise's management system and its impact. , which is not reflected in existing approaches as a component of the development resource.

Starting the process of strategic development is based on the enterprise's response to environmental problems through the allocation of resources [1]. At the same time, the management system is one of the main components of development and a necessary condition for a positive result of strategy implementation. Therefore, the main parameters of its situation should be reflected in the information supply system of the company's development strategy.

Based on the above circumstances, a model of information provision of the innovative development strategy of the enterprise aimed at forming and providing the necessary information for the development and management of innovation-based development processes was proposed. This model is designed to provide the necessary management information for the development and implementation stages of the strategic innovative development process of the enterprise, including the parameters of the management system, management information that reflects its

condition in terms of ensuring balance in its development. covers technical, technological and organizational-management areas [4].

In order for the information supply system of the enterprise's innovation strategy to enable it to solve the tasks assigned to it, it is necessary to determine its main parameters expressed by the following:

- structure of information systems and management reports that reflect information about innovation processes in the necessary aspects;
- the form and list of management reports that ensure the completeness and comprehensibility of the presented information that can be practically used for making management decisions;
- Hierarchy of information movement from direct executors of innovation processes to those who make management decisions.

As an expression of providing information to the innovative strategy of the industrial enterprise, it is proposed to use a set of management forms reflecting the aspects of the innovative strategy. As the main form of management, it is suggested to consider the strategic map of enterprise development. It is characterized by the main indicators of the enterprise strategy (finance, marketing, internal business processes, personnel) for the reflected development prospects together with the planned activities of innovative projects.

The implementation model of the innovation strategy information provision model is shown in Fig. 1.

Figure 1. Model of information provision of innovative strategy of industrial enterprises (author's development)

This combination of elements of the management system, which are interconnected and located in a single analytical department and information space, ensures timely acquisition of all information necessary for effective management decisions in the process of development strategy development and implementation. provides [6]. Through the budget system, planning and management of indicators of the innovation strategy, in general and its separate structural links, as well as assessment of business efficiency and effectiveness are carried out. An addition to the information support system is a block of the monitoring system aimed at "monitoring" the important aspects of the economic entity's activity that are not reflected in the forms of management accounting, for example, in the market situation.

The advantages of the proposed model of information provision of the innovative development strategy are as follows:

- the model is based on the synergy of individual information components of the strategy, which is expressed not only in the structure of planned and actual information flows, but also in obtaining additional efficiency due to accuracy, transparency, speed in making management decisions;

- organization of mutual cooperation within the framework of the information supply system does not require a fundamental change in the existing structure and functionality of the enterprise;

- the possibility of achieving "quick" results: creating a model at the initial stage allows correcting "inconsistencies" in the existing information support system and filling in missing information links;

- model is based on the clear definition of the main blocks of information, each of them is designed to provide certain information. Such a structure of management information provides clarification of information when making management decisions based on it, and also determines the causal relationship between individual blocks.

In accordance with the model of information provision of the innovative strategy, there should be a constant exchange of information between the budgeting, management and accounting systems. The basis for the formation of management accounting information is the interaction of the budget and accounting systems as the main source of obtaining real information on the implementation of the development strategy. In order for management accounting to reflect all the necessary information, it is important to clearly define the information channels of the actual "flow" of accounting information. Accounting should become an integral part of management accounting from the point of view of presenting factual

information in the prescribed manner. In this way, it is necessary to change the procedure for using accounts of production costs, as well as to modernize accounting, which consists in organizing and unifying the set of analytical features used in these accounts [5].

Graphically, the main levels of the hierarchy of information supply system users of the innovation strategy are shown in Figure 2.

Figure 2. Levels of information provision of innovative strategy users (author's development)

The innovative strategy of the enterprise is related not only to the distribution of material resources, but also to the distribution of the efforts of the enterprise's management apparatus to simultaneously manage innovative and traditional areas of activity. This is important, on the one hand, in ensuring reasonable workload of management personnel, and on the other hand, in ensuring timely response to deviations in planned processes in the form of effective management decisions.

The model is implemented at several levels. The first level is the level of heads of departments, in the main components of which the necessary set of basic management forms reflecting the aspects of the innovation strategy is formed. This

level is the most "saturated" in terms of information, since it is here that the initial filling of planned and actual data by direct executors of work on development projects takes place.

The main purpose of the separate level of information provision is to provide preliminary information that is the basis for developing a development strategy and monitoring its implementation. The second level is the level of heads of functional areas where management forms are combined and main reports are compiled in the main functional areas of innovative activity. The third level is the upper-top level of management, which is characterized by a lack of management forms that contain information that reflects the development strategy based on innovative projects. The control data selection list provided here is shortened and their content expanded. Conclusions and suggestions.

The practical application of the proposed model of information provision of the innovative strategy used in the management of industrial enterprises makes it possible to:

- ensuring the transparency of the company's development strategy and its management accordingly;
- information flows within the innovation strategy systematization and regulation;
- control and management of financial flows both within the framework of the innovative strategy and throughout the enterprise;
- tracking innovation costs with any level of detail by origin and effectively managing them;
- assessment of the effectiveness of the balanced innovation strategy of enterprise development.

The proposed model of information support requires the creation of appropriate practical tools that allow it to be "transferred" from the conceptual category to the practical category in order to find direct application in the formulation of the development strategy and subsequent implementation. . The novelty of this model allows it to be connected with organizational and management innovations, which is the formatting of the management accounting system represented by the integration, budgeting and monitoring systems and the innovative activity accounting system in a single information department. In this regard, within the framework of the implementation of the innovative strategy, it is necessary to provide the management system with the necessary information base for making effective management decisions.

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